

The Laws and Ideologies Governing Forensic Science

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Introduction

Utilizing scientific concepts to examine evidence in legal settings, forensic science is an interdisciplinary field. It provides unbiased, scientific analysis of several kinds of evidence, which is vital to criminal investigations. Here is a summary of the several branches of forensic science: Investigating crimes is the main emphasis of the scientific field of forensic science. Criminal procedure and justifiability of evidence are the guiding principles of the nation's legal system. A great number of violators escaped punishment because the antiquated court system lacked standardized forensic techniques. Nonetheless, forensic science in the legal domain evolved as its significance increased. In order to address questions that may be questioned in a court of law, forensic science is the scientific field that recognizes, identifies, individualizes, and evaluates physical evidence using the rules and guidelines of natural science. From the time a crime is committed until the accused is found guilty in a court of law, these forensic science concepts directly affect criminal procedures.

Describe Forensic Science.

Gathering and analyzing evidence using a scientific approach to establish facts for legal purposes is known as forensic science, or forensics. It integrates ideas from several scientific fields to provide answers to legal situation

n-related queries. Seeking the truth and offering unbiased proof that is admissible in court are the principal objectives.

Locard's Principle of Exchange:

"Every single contact creates a mark" is the fundamental tenet of forensic science, and it is credited to the French scientist Edmond Locard, a pioneer in the fields of criminology and forensic research. According to Locard, there are a lot of traces that can yield the most important information when they are properly evaluated. As per this theory, any time an offender or their weapon of choice comes into contact with the victim, his surroundings, or objects, traces of the crime are left behind. The same contact also left traces that the criminal or his weaponry picked up. For instance, blood stains can be found in the vehicle that was involved in a hit-and-run collision and fled the scene. Similar to this, the victim's surroundings will have vehicle paint, tyre and shoe marks. An further well-known instance is the bloodstain or seminal stain observed in the rape victim, while hair is visible on the accused's body.

Technological investigation of crimes is based on this statute. Every situation where there is contact—such as with fingerprints, tyre marks, bullet remnants, foot marks, hair samples, skin, muscles, body fluids, blood, articles of clothing, etc.—validates this theory. A simple application of this theory is DNA analysis, where any such objects under examination are thought to be in the perpetrator's possession.

The law of Uniqueness:

The idea is recognized as the foundation of forensic science and is credited to Paul L. Kirk (1963). This law suggests that all entities—persons and objects alike—are distinct and individualistic. There is no such thing as a natural or manufactured duplicate. Even the things that God has created, like plants, seeds, and fruits, are distinct. Example: Although they may appear to be similar or identical, the coins, banknotes, typewriting's, etc. are all unique.

Forensic science, according to Kirk, is concerned with determining the origin of two things (known and questioned, or mark and print) that are assumed to have originated from the same source. Therefore, identification is not about two objects being the same; rather, it is about proving

individuality from traces left at a crime scene. Thus, by examining traces and samples, identity can be demonstrated indirectly. For example, no two fingerprints are alike.

The Law of Gradual Transformation

It has a huge effect on criminal investigations. Over time, the criminals experience gradual transformations. The only things that will identify the criminal if he is not caught in time are his fingerprints, blood types from stains, and DNA profile. The crime scene is likewise undergoing a fast transformation. If the crime scene is not secured, tangible evidence may be misplaced, tampered with, or destroyed, leaving the scene unrecognizable.

The Law of Equivalence

Comparing different samples should only be done with similar samples. To put it another way, fibers are compared to other fibers, blood samples are compared to other blood samples, and so on. A shotgun cannot be compared, for instance, to a bullet recovered from the murder scene. Similarly, if writing is to be inspected, it must be compared to other similar writing on a wall rather than on paper. This is because different people will write differently on paper and the wall in terms of size and alignment.

The Law of Assessment:

For the purpose of analysis, the legislation addresses how to properly gather and store samples in order to prevent manipulation or destruction. For the simple reason that the calibre of the sample being analyzed, its chain of custody, and the analyst's experience all affect the calibre of any analysis. For instance, the investigating officer gathering the blood-stained clothing will be useless in the event of a seminal stain study. In order to identify the explosive material, it is necessary to test residual materials that were gathered from the explosion scene and contain the materialistic substance of the blast. Testing soil alone would not be useful in this situation.

Probability Law:

Depending on the situation, all of the identifications and identities are occasionally accurate, both consciously and unconsciously. Also, the conclusions drawn from forensic analysis depend on the method used and its pros and disadvantages. These need to be considered. A mathematical concept

called probability establishes the likelihood that an event will occur in a given manner among multiple possible outcomes. For instance, in the instance of identifying the lifeless body of a woman wearing spectacles, who had a nose piercing and a tattoo on her right arm. In summary, the entire purpose of forensic analysis is to find traces and link them to specific people. It is not possible to identify suspects at a crime scene if traces are not found. If traces are found, though, they can be used as evidence if they are properly analysed and the results are interpreted.

The Law of Inferred Facts

This pertains to victim statements, eyewitness accounts, and other related matters. Whenever someone is asked to present proof, there is a possibility that the information they provide is unreliable. This may occur accidentally (by inaccurate observations or assumptions) or on purpose (by lying or exaggerating). Conversely, evidence that provides a factual narrative (derived from an investigation) is more likely to be accurate and trustworthy. In light of this, forensic science is a branch of science that uses natural science concepts and techniques to identify, assess, individualize, and recognize physical evidence in order to administer criminal justice.

Improvements Needed:

Due to a dearth of judicial work culture, there is insufficient empirical evidence to back up this notion in relation to medical evidence. Consequently, a pilot study was created to evaluate the time and effort medical professionals expended in obtaining evidence to be recorded in criminal courts, along with other related matters.

The Malimath Committee proposed amending a few sections of the Criminal Procedure Code to incorporate the principles of forensic science. These included creating a separate police regulation that would set uniform guidelines for obtaining genetic information and establishing the safeguards required to prevent its exploitation. In order to combat terrorism, it is highly suggested that a national DNA database be constructed. More state-of-the-art laboratories should be built in order to handle evidence and DNA samples. Public education, courts, prosecutors, and law enforcement should all be given more attention. Establishing and updating the "General Criteria for Laboratory Accreditation" is necessary in order to accredit forensic science laboratories because of the

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multidisciplinary nature of the work that is done at these facilities. A Technical Committee that was specifically established for this purpose created the "Specific Criteria for Accreditation of Forensic Science Laboratories" document.

Conclusion:

This article explores the core legal theories that support forensic science and influence the validity and admissibility of evidence in court actions. The seven main rules and guidelines that are covered are: In forensic chemistry, distinct properties are essential for accurate identification of all objects. Similar items can be compared, which is especially useful when dealing with biological samples like blood and allows for a thorough inspection for identification. All of these ideas come together to create a solid foundation that supports the criminal justice system and directs forensic investigators. The strict observance of these regulations guarantees that forensic evidence satisfies the most stringent requirements for validity and court admissibility. The complex world of forensic science rules and their significant influence on the pursuit of justice are recommended reading for readers. Acquiring knowledge of these principles not only broadens one's perspective on the intricacies of forensic investigations, but also clarifies the vital function they fulfil in maintaining the integrity of legal procedures.

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